

Synthesis and structural studies of new organometallic compounds of ruthenium(II) and -(IV) containing disulfidothionitrato (S_3N^-) ligand

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Organoruthenium complexes containing terminal SS donor bidentate disulfidothionitrato (S_3N^-) have been synthesised. The bonding ability and strength of each metal-ligand (M-L) bond in each complex have been studied using mean amplitude of vibrational technique derived from Cyvin and Kimura's equation.

The findings of the work on the synthesis and structural characterisation of six disulfidothionitrato (S_3N^-) organo-metal compounds of ruthenium(II) and -(IV) are reported here.

Results and Discussion

All the six disulfidothionitratoruthenium complexes were found air-stable, diamagnetic solids, soluble in CH_2Cl_2 , CH_3CN and insoluble in other organic solvents (viz. $CHCl_3$, hexane, ether, petroleum ether). The diamagnetic behaviour and bidentate bonding mode via two sulphur atoms of the S_3N^- group suggest that the oxidation state of the ruthenium is two and four. The very low conductivity of the complexes ($4-6 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ in acetonitrile) eliminates their ionic character and consequently interpreted according to Geary¹ as being non-electrolytes. These findings are also supported by the theoretical calculations of mean amplitude of vibration² at room temperature. Decomposition temperature, yield and colour of the complexes are summarised under syntheses which support their stoichiometry.

The ir spectra of these complexes contain strong bands at $992-1020$ and $700-740 cm^{-1}$ due to ν_{NS} and $580-600 cm^{-1}$ due to ν_{S-S} which are in close agreement with the values of coordinated bidentate S_3N^- ligand reported in the literature^{3,4}. The low frequency ir spectra of the complexes show two bands at $380-304 cm^{-1}$ assignable to ν_{Ru-Cl} . The absorption at the highest energy may be assigned to the ν_{Ru-Cl} stretch *trans* to the organic moiety group and lower energy to the ν_{Ru-Cl} stretch probably *trans* to S_3N^- ion. The band at $415-475 cm^{-1}$ is assignable to ν_{Ru-S} . All the complexes exhibited the characteristic bands of organic ligand (viz. C_5H_5 , C_6H_6 , C_7H_8 , C_8H_{10})^{1,4} besides the specific bands of triphenyl phosphine [(PPh₃)Ru(S_3N)Cl]. Thus, ir absorption bands due to S_3N^- ligand are in close agreement with the values for bidentate S_3N^- ligand suggesting the

structure as shown in Fig. 1 and display the structure of intercalation⁵ compound.

Fig. 1 Bonding mode of S_3N^- (as bidentate) ligand with Ru-metal, M = Ru and $\phi = C_5H_5$, C_6H_6 , PPh₃, C_7H_8 , C_8H_{10}

In order to investigate the relative bonding ability in all the six disulfidothionitrato-organoruthenium compounds, the room temperature (300 K) mean amplitude values for Ru- ϕ , Ru-S, S-N, S-S and Ru-Cl were calculated and summarised in Table 1. From this table, we can account for the relative bonding ability of the organic moiety (C_5H_5 , C_6H_6 , C_7H_8 , C_8H_{10} , PPh₃) and S_3N^- species. The variation of the amplitude values (u) for the complexes (1-6) follows the sequence: 1, Ru-S > Ru- C_5H_5 > S-S > S-N; 2, Ru-Cl > Ru-S > S-S > S-N > Ru- C_6H_6 ; 3, Ru-Cl > S-S > Ru-S > S-N > Ru-PPh₃; 4, Ru-S > Ru-Cl > S-S > S-N > Ru- C_7H_8 ; 5, Ru-Cl > S-S > Ru-S > S-N > Ru- C_8H_{10} ; 6, Ru-Cl > Ru-S > S-S > S-N. It has been established^{2,6} that lower the u -value, stronger is the M-L bond. Obviously, organic moieties are strongly bonded to Ru-metal as compared to S_3N^- species. Among different organic π -ligands, the bonding ability sequence is $C_6H_6 > C_8H_{10} > C_7H_8 > C_5H_5$. Thus, Ru- C_6H_6 (chd group) bonding is strongest and Ru- C_5H_5 (cp) bonding is weakest in the organoruthenium compounds under investigation. In compound 3 the bonding ability of PPh₃ is stronger than S_3N^- species and Cl atoms. These evidences suggest that S_3N^- acts as a bidentate ligand representing an important class of cyclometallothiazenes whose bonding

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Table 1. Room temperature (300 K) mean amplitude of vibration ($\mu \times 10^3$) for disulfidothionitrato-organoruthenium(II) and (IV) compounds at different vibrational frequencies

no.	Compd.	$\mu \times 10^3$				
		Ru- ϕ	S-N	S-S	Ru-S	Ru-Cl
1.	$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ru}(\text{S}_3\text{N})]$ ($\phi = \text{C}_5\text{H}_5$)	45.29 (800 cm^{-1})	42.06 (995 cm^{-1})	43.85 (610 cm^{-1})	46.06 (425 cm^{-1})	-
2.	$[(\pi\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{S}_3\text{N})\text{Cl}]$ ($\phi = \text{C}_6\text{H}_6$)	28.03 (2000 cm^{-1})	41.61 (1015 cm^{-1})	43.35 (580 cm^{-1})	46.91 (415 cm^{-1})	48.37 (380 cm^{-1})
3.	$[(\text{PPh}_3)\text{Ru}(\text{S}_3\text{N})\text{Cl}]$ ($\phi = \text{PPh}_3$)	33.29 (690 cm^{-1})	41.50 (1020 cm^{-1})	44.33 (600 cm^{-1})	42.69 (470 cm^{-1})	57.27 (310 cm^{-1})
4.	$[(\pi\text{-C}_7\text{H}_8)\text{Ru}(\text{S}_3\text{N})\text{Cl}]$ ($\phi = \text{C}_7\text{H}_8$)	28.46 (1940 cm^{-1})	41.84 (1005 cm^{-1})	44.98 (587 cm^{-1})	68.26 (265 cm^{-1})	55.45 (322 cm^{-1})
5.	$[(\pi\text{-C}_8\text{H}_{10})\text{Ru}(\text{S}_3\text{N})\text{Cl}]$ ($\phi = \text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}$)	28.32 (1960 cm^{-1})	41.61 (1015 cm^{-1})	44.33 (600 cm^{-1})	44.09 (450 cm^{-1})	58.24 (304 cm^{-1})
6.	$[\text{Ru}(\text{S}_3\text{N})\text{Cl}]$	-	42.06 (995 cm^{-1})	44.33 (600 cm^{-1})	45.64 (430 cm^{-1})	55.02 (325 cm^{-1})

strength is weaker than π -organic ligands and loosely bonded to Ru-metal.

Experimental

The synthesis of organometallic complexes of the type $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ru}]$, $[(\pi\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{RuCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)]$, $[(\pi\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{RuCl}_2]_2$, $[(\pi\text{-C}_7\text{H}_8)\text{RuCl}_2]_2$ and $[(\pi\text{-C}_8\text{H}_{10})\text{RuCl}_2]_2$ were carried out by modified literature⁷ procedure. Manipulations were done dry oxygen-free nitrogen using standard Schlenk apparatus. The solvents were dried by standard procedure⁸ and freshly distilled before use. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 881 spectrometer. The conductance was measured on an Elico CM 82T conductivity bridge in acetonitrile solution.

The pale yellow crystals of hepta sulfurimide (S_7NH) were obtained from dichlorodisulfane (S_2Cl_2) and ammonia (NH_3) in dimethyl formamide (DMF) by modified literature procedure⁵,

Synthesis of S_3N^- complexes: The reaction of a blue solution⁹ of S_7NH in DMF (4.0 ml) was carried out separately with each of the above mentioned five organometallic compounds in 1 : 1 molar ratio in DMF (2.0 ml) solvent. In each case, the reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h till its colour changed to dull green or brown green. The filtrate was concentrated to half of its original volume under reduced pressure and then diethyl ether (50 ml) was added to yield brown mass from which the complexes were obtained corresponding to the formulae $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ru}(\text{S}_3\text{N})]$,

$[(\pi\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{S}_3\text{N})\text{Cl}] + [\text{Ru}(\text{S}_3\text{N})\text{Cl}]$, $[(\pi\text{-C}_7\text{H}_8)\text{Ru}(\text{S}_3\text{N})\text{Cl}]$, and $[(\pi\text{-C}_8\text{H}_{10})\text{Ru}(\text{S}_3\text{N})\text{Cl}]$, respectively. The compound $[\text{Ru}(\text{S}_3\text{N})\text{Cl}]$ was separated from $[(\pi\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}(\text{S}_3\text{N})\text{Cl}]$ using CH_2Cl_2 solvent : yield, 35–45%, decomp. temp., 120–40°; gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

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